

of multiple of those cues may increase the chance, that external-motion may be perceived as self-motion [3].

Their technique rotates the virtual environment around the user in such a way, that the user is made to always walk towards the farthest wall of the tracking area. In theory and with a tracking area large enough, according to Razzaque et al., it should be possible to present a virtual environment of infinite extent. However, with a decrease of tracking area, eventually more rotation has to be applied to the virtual environment, to keep the user within the physical perimeter of the tracking area and each increase of applied rotation also increases the chance of detecting the manipulation. The thresholds for applied rotational distortion is therefore an tradeoff between a lower detection probability and less physical space requirement.

Razzaque et al. even claim, that "Even while standing still, the user unknowingly rotates her head and torso with the virtual scene" and assume, that the explanation lies within the user's own balance system in regard to [2].

Within their experiment, which is often referred to as the first working case of RDW [4], Razzaque et al. used a head mounted display with stereo headphones to present the visuals and spatialized audio. Users had to reach a way point, then first turn towards the next way point, before moving straight towards that new way point without wandering around. During these turns towards the next way point, a rotational scaling was applied to the representation of the virtual environment to point the user towards the direction she came from, while making her see, hear and believe, that she turned towards a point further down the hallway. The blue box in figure 1 shows the path, the user has taken within the virtual environment. The red box below shows the path she took within the tracking area at the same time. Small misalignments after the turns were corrected by further applying small rotational distortions while the user was walking towards the next target. This explains the arcs in figure 1. So while actually walking back and forth in a rather small physical room, the user had the impression of having passed through a significantly larger area. This experiment should also work for a virtual hallway of infinite length.

2.2 An algorithm to dynamically apply gains

The algorithm used in [1] is shown in figure 2. As mentioned before, in [1] users even compensated for small amounts of rotational distortion to the virtual environment while standing still. This is the *baseline constant rotation* and the first of three basic factors to the resulting rotational distortion. The other two are a scaling to the users real rotation and a rotation proportional to the users linear velocity (i. e. walking speed), but only the maximum of those three would find consideration and be scaled by the sine of the angle between the next virtual target and the next real target. Finally the resulting distortion rate was limited by a fixed threshold, which was determined as being the threshold for imperceptible rotational distortion by previous tests.

2.3 The human locomotion triple

In [5] Steinicke et al. introduce the user's locomotion triple (in [6] then named human locomotion triple (HLT)). The HLT consists of three normalized vectors: (s, u, w) . The strafe vector s is orthogonal to the walking direction and parallel to the

Figure 2. The algorithm for computing the rotational distortion rate. Figure taken from [1].

Figure 3. The curvature gain bends a path and the rotation gain scales a rotation.

walking plane, the up vector u represents the tracked head orientation and the walk-direction vector w represents the tracked direction of walk. Through the HLT, manipulations can be applied to users' paths by various gains as described during the next sections.

2.4 Gains to manipulate the users' movements

While the tracking system constantly provides up-to-date data for the users real world position and orientation defined as P_{real} and R_{real} , the translation is defined by

$$T_{real} = P_{cur} - P_{pre}$$

where P_{cur} is the current real position and P_{pre} the previous/last considered real position. A translation gain $g_T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is defined for each component of the HLT: $g_T[s], g_T[u], g_T[w]$ by

$$g_T := \frac{T_{virtual}}{T_{real}}$$

By such gains the mapping of real world movements (in this last case translations) can be scaled up or down, depending on the values of the gain. A $g_T < 1$ would result in a smaller translation within the virtual world ($T_{virtual}$) in respect to the

tracked translation in the real world (T_{real}), while a $g_T > 1$ would result in a larger translation in the virtual world and such enabling the users to cover a larger virtual distance. A $g_T = 1$ would draw the real world and the virtual world to scale as if no gain was applied at all.

In the same manner, Steinicke et al. introduce gains for rotation, curvature and displacement as well as time-dependent gains. Rotation gains are applied to rotations of the head and result in a greater or smaller rotation of the virtual world, while a rotation of the head is tracked, as illustrated in figure 3b. Rotation gains are defined by the quotient of the considered component of a virtual world rotation $R_{virtual}$ and the real world rotation R_{real} :

$$g_R := \frac{R_{virtual}}{R_{real}}$$

The curvature gain stimulates users to unknowingly walk an arc in the tracking area while walking on a straight line in the virtual environment even when she does not willingly rotate, as illustrated in figure 3a. curvature gains are defined by a segment of a circle with the radius r :

$$g_C := \frac{1}{r}$$

Displacement gains map real world rotations into virtual world translations ($R_{real} \Rightarrow T_{virtual}$). Time-dependent gains can be defined like all the other gains, though they are not triggered by real world movements, but by time elapsed. The virtual environment is manipulated with no regard to the users movements and such even when she is not moving at all.

2.5 Experiments for detecting thresholds

In March 2008 Steinicke et al. published results of a pilot study [7] within a tracking area of 10m x 7m x 2.5m, in which they identified the following thresholds for RDW without letting the users notice the manipulation:

- Rotations can be compressed or gained up to 30%,
- distances can be downscaled to 15% and upscaled to 45%,
- users can be redirected to unknowingly walk on a circle with a radius as small as 3.3m,
- objects and the virtual environment can be downscaled to 38% and upscaled to 45%.

2.6 Non-visual redirected walking by acoustic stimuli

While a lot of research has been committed to RDW during the last couple of years, almost all contributions are based upon the visualization of the virtual environment as primary stimuli. Some authors state, that the acoustic factor helps users to adjust to the virtual world and that RDW works best, when multiple cues, such as vestibular, visual and auditory, are consistent with each other, as this helps the user to perceive external-motion as self-motion [3, 1]. Even though, the auditory aspect had been paid little attention so far [8].

Razzaque et al. used circumaural stereo headphones to deliver spatialized environmental sounds and prerecorded instructions to the user, where the sounds were intended to be "plausible in both content and source location". The analysis of the effect

of the sound was limited to the lack of negative comments by the users [1].

Steinicke et al. used ambient city noise to mask real sounds, but auditory cues were not used to directly aid the RDW technique [9, 6, 10]. A lot of contributions do not mention auditory components at all.

To our knowledge, currently Serafin et al. are the only ones, who really concentrated on the auditory component of RDW techniques. They conducted two different experiments to determine thresholds for acoustic based RDW techniques [8]. To that goal, they adapted two of the experiments conducted in [9, 10], to be used exclusively with auditory feedback. Their experimental setup consisted of a surround system with 16 MB5A Dynaudio speakers in a circular array with a diameter of 1.7 meters, and subjects wore an deactivated head mounted display (HMD) to block out their vision. The only audible feedback in both experiments was the sound of an alarm clock. This choice was meant to be especially fitting, since the sounds of alarm clocks are usually associated with stationary objects and often occur in darkened otherwise quiet places. The sound was delivered through the speaker array by the technique of vector base amplitude panning (VBAP), which, in such a setup, allows the placement of sounds within the circular array of speakers on a plane parallel to the ground level

The first experiment tested the ability to detect rotation gains during self-motion rotations on the spot. The second experiment tested the detection of curvature gains while walking on a virtually straight line while walking from one point on the perimeter of the circular speaker array to a point roughly on the opposite side. Due to the limited space, only short distanced could be covered during each test.

During the first experiment the subjects were asked to turn on the spot towards the sound of the alarm clock. While they were turning, a rotation gain would rotate the alarm clock around the subjects. When they perceived the sound as in front of them, they were asked whether they perceived the virtual rotation as larger (rotation gain < 0) or smaller (rotation gain > 0), than the real world rotation. The virtual rotation is perceived through auditory cues by locating the position of the sound source, while the real rotation mainly by the vestibular system. During the 22 subsequent trials per test subject, 11 different rotation gains were applied. Each gain was applied twice during the course of an experiment. For the evaluation Serafin et al. followed Steinicke et al. [10] and used a psychometric function to determine a bias for the point of subjective equality (PSE). The PSE, where subjects perceived the real and virtual rotation as equal, was determined at 1. Serafin et al. also chose an outbalance of 75% to 25% of the given answers as the detection threshold and these thresholds were reached at gains of 0.82 for greater and 1.2 for smaller responses. This led them to the conclusion, that users can not reliably distinguish between a 90° real rotation and a virtual rotation between 75° and 109°. So users can be turned 20% more or 18% less than the perceived virtual rotation. This range is smaller than the one determined in [10], which can be attributed to the fact, that "[...] vision generally is considered superior to audition when it comes to the estimation of spatial location of objects." Goldstein [11] cited by Serafin [8]. In other words, visual cues dominate vestibular, proprioceptive, etc. cues by more,

than auditory cues would and therefore discrepancies between visual and other cues would be accepted to a higher degree.

During the second experiment users were asked to walk on a straight line towards the alarm clock. During their movement 10 different curvature gains were applied (each one twice), which led them on an arced real path and users were asked whether and at which threshold they notice the direction of the bended path reliably. During this experiment the PSE was determined at a curvature gain of -5. The detection thresholds of 75% were reached at gains of -25 and 30 [8].

3. CHOICE OF GAINS TO BE TESTED

This section explains, how the gains for the experiment at hand were selected.

In [6] Steinicke et al. explain five different types of gains to manipulate users' movements within a redirected walking application: the translation gain, rotation gain, curvature gain, displacement gain and time-dependent gain. Time-dependent gains however have to be subdivided into at least time-dependent rotation gains and time-dependent translation gains.

Translation gains, as a means to scale translations and described in [6] were not considered for these experiments for long, since the acoustic perception of distance of humans is much worse than the visual perception. It is presumed, that vast manipulations can be made with translation gains but that these will most likely not be perceived as a different self-motion. Much rather, the initial distance to the object might be perceived differently and such give the impression of false dimensions of the virtual environment. This might be interesting for acoustic RDW applications in general but is not considered as one of the main methods. More interesting might be a version of the translation gain, which translates i. e. physical forward movements into virtual displacements orthogonal to the walking direction, which would have an effect close to the one of the curvature gain. To keep the amount of tests for each test person in check and because of the close relatedness to the curvature gain it would not become part of this study either.

The displacement gain specifies physical rotations to virtual translations, which might be useful in some situations but will most likely not become a significant part in most redirected walking application, due to high detection of the displacement or in conclusion small manipulation potential.

Time-dependent translation gains have been neglected due to the reasons stated above. Time-dependent rotation gains have been considered and were part of a pilot study, but were discarded, because no test subjects compensated for the manipulations.

Curvature gains and even more so rotation gains seem to be the most promising and raised the most attention so far, next to translation gains [5, 7, 12, 6, 8]. Especially Serafin et al. also concentrated on these two types of gains during their work about acoustic RDW [8]. The self conducted pilot studies also showed great potential for acoustic tests with the wave field synthesis system (WFS system) and therefore these two types became the center of this research.

Figure 3a illustrates an example of a bended path by the appliance of an curvature gain. The user perceives the virtual path as straight, while she really walks on a curved path. Figure 3b illustrates an example of a scaled rotation by the appliance of

an rotation gain. The user perceives the rotation as 180°, but really only rotates by 90°.

4. THE LABORATORY

This section will give a brief overview of the laboratory, in which the experiment will be conducted. An illustration of the laboratory can be found in figure 4 and a more detailed description in [13].

The area of the WFS system is defined by the speaker arrays and covers roughly 5x6 meters. The height of the lower edges of the speakers is just over 2 meters. The reproduction component of the system consists of 26 speaker modules which contain 676 single speakers equally divided amongst 208 channels. The distance between the centers of the channels within each speaker array is 10 cm. All modules are slightly tilted downwards and both of the 6 meter arrays and one of the 5 meter arrays is backed by a wall of the room.

The tracking area is defined by six infrared cameras which are arranged in a square formation of 4x4 meters parallel to the ground in the height of about 2.5 meters with the two extra cameras mounted below two adjoining corners at about 1.5 meters height. All cameras are roughly aligned towards the middle of the tracking area. Due to the range of the cameras, the tracking area is slightly larger than the 4x4 square but the tracking is most robust within these boundaries.

Figure 4. Layout of the laboratory with 26 audio modules and 6 infrared cameras.

The WFS terminal is located in one of the corners of the room. The terminal serves as the primary user interface for the WFS system. Within are also all instances and programs for playing back sounds, propagating commands and rendering for the speaker modules. The main digital audio workstations (DAWs) in use are Ardour¹ and Cubase².

5. THE EXPERIMENT DESIGN

This section will explain the prepared experiment, starting with the requirements followed by a description of the test procedure, and closing with the choice of gain values and different test groups.

5.1 Requirements

Some basic requirements had to be met during development of the experiment, to enable success.

¹ <https://ardour.org/>

² www.steinberg.net/de/products/cubase/

- Virtual ambient noise
 - To mask laboratory noises...
 - and to help perceive the external-motion as self-motion.
- Sounds, that stimulate the test persons to turn on the spot.
- Sounds, that stimulate the test persons to walk.

5.1.1 Ambient noise

The ambient noise has two main purposes. The first purpose is to mask laboratory noises, and the second purpose is to give more acoustic cues for orientation and essentially to make the RDW manipulations more plausible. The majority of experiments referred to in section 2 (Related Work) used headphones to play back the acoustic aspects of the immersive virtual environment. In [9] for example headphones were used to play back some kind of ambient city noise "such that an orientation by means of auditory feedback in the real world was not possible" and in [4] noise-canceling headphones playing white noise were used to mask real ambient noise. For RDW by WFS noise-canceling headphones are out of the question, since they would, of course, cancel out the acoustic cues for the techniques as well. Actually, any kind of headphones were considered disturbing and unnecessary. Instead, four virtual sound sources were used to play back the ambient sounds through the same medium as the sounds to direct the test subjects. Through the WFS system. For the ambient sounds, linear sound sources were chosen. Through the randomized sequence of the successive tests, that will be performed and explained later in this section, the path of the test subjects within the consistent virtual environment can not be foreseen. Test subjects could therefore close in on these virtual sound source during their tasks. If they were point sound sources, the test subjects would notice that and if they got too close, they could disturb the experiment, as they are not meant to be located within the focus of the test subjects. Linear sound sources however merely define a direction for the sound, which does not change when test subjects get close to them.

The four linear sound sources were oriented towards the four cardinal directions. Two opposite sound sources were mapped to the same but phase shifted monotonous city noise with some cars driving by but little distinctive aspects³. Their main function is, to mask the laboratory noises. One of the other sources got the sound of a playground⁴ and the opposite one of a small pedestrian zone⁵. These are mainly meant to give some secondary orientation.

5.1.2 Sounds to turn

To stimulate the test subjects to turn, the sound of a small constantly barking dog⁶ was chosen and mapped to the turn-to target. Any sound would have sufficed, but intuitively people would turn and look towards a barking dog and it appears plausible, that this dog may change its position, such giving more freedom in designing the experiment while staying somewhat plausible.

³ <https://www.freesound.org/people/balou82/sounds/184356/>

⁴ <https://www.freesound.org/people/music.boy/sounds/119121/>

⁵ <https://www.freesound.org/people/mario1298/sounds/155346/>

⁶ <https://www.freesound.org/people/felix.blume/sounds/199261/> (This sound was modified to provide more regularity)

5.1.3 Sounds to walk

As a sound to stimulate the test persons to walk somewhere the sound of an ice cream truck⁷ was chosen and mapped to the go-to target. Again, any sound would have sufficed but in addition to the dog, this seemed like a plausible choice.

5.2 Automated test sequence

To meet these requirements, an automation was designed, which leads the test subjects through all the tests of their experiment. This section starts with the conditions, the automation will have to meet and finally describes the sequence of the automation.

5.2.1 Conditions

One fundamental goal of the experiment design was to conduct all tests for a test subject in one piece without breaks in presences. At no time during the experiment, test subjects should use other cues but aural, vestibular or proprioceptive cues. Some tests however have certain demands towards the starting position and / or orientation of the test subject. A curvature gain test for example can not start with the test subject facing a wall. For these tests, prior to defining the individual starting position and orientation, a likely path of the test subject will have to be predicted. While rotation gains could theoretically be tested in any position and angle, some aspects led to a closer definition of the starting conditions. The height of virtual sound sources within this WFS system is not position preservative. While auditors move through the plane, the perceived elevation of the virtual sound sources is dependent of the proximity to the relevant speakers. A virtual sound source outside of the physical WFS area will always be "behind" one of the speakers (see figure 5a). The speaker can be seen as the angle point of a seesaw with the aural perception system of an auditor on one side and the virtual sound source on the other side, as illustrated in figure 5. While the slope of this seesaw and decreases with the proximity of the auditor to the relevant speaker, the perceived elevation of the virtual sound source also in- and decreases (see figure 5). The slope also changes, when the virtual sound source moves behind other speakers which are closer to or further away from the auditor. Since this effect presumably can give cues about the movement of virtual sound sources, rotation gain tests are defined to always take place in the center of the physical WFS area, where the variation of the distance between auditor and speaker, as well as between virtual sound source and speaker is least.

5.2.2 Path Prediction

For curvature gain tests, it is crucial to predict the path, the test subject is likely to take during the test. Even though the ideal path, given a starting position, starting orientation and curvature gain value, can be calculated, it is highly unlikely, that the test subject will take this ideal path, considering that the RDW technique is based on the principle of leading users to believe, that they strayed from the path. Amongst others, aspects like the precision of detecting the direction of the targeted virtual sound source and the responsiveness to the manipulations will

⁷ <https://www.freesound.org/people/erictrausser/sounds/106238/> (This sound was cut, at the beginning and the end of the tune)

(a) Virtual sound sources are located on a straight defined by virtual sound sources seem to head and speaker. (b) As the auditor is moving, the height of virtual sound sources change their height.

Figure 5. The height of virtual sound sources is dependent on the relative position of the auditor to the relevant speakers. While the auditor moves closer to the speaker, the red virtual sound source will stay between the head and the speaker and such changing its height for this auditor.

Figure 6. All possible starting positions for curvature gain and rotation gain tests with corresponding orientations.

influence the path the test subject is going to take. Minor manipulations will be calculated in a rapid succession, which are always dependent on the current position of the test subject and such, even the ideal path changes with every stray from the previous ideal path.

Even though the exact path, which the test subject is going to take can not be foreseen, an estimation can be made. The value of the curvature gain determines, in which direction the test subject will be redirected. Assumed the test subject is oriented towards the target before the test starts, it is highly unlikely, that she will veer into the opposite direction by an significant amount. So the path ahead and towards the direction of the manipulation should be free. These tests will therefore start in corners of the room with an orientation towards the adjacent corner, which opens the room towards the direction of the manipulation. Figure 6 illustrates the possible starting positions and orientations.

5.2.3 Automation

The automation is to ensure, that all test will be executed in a random order seamlessly and without any further instructions or interferences during the experiment. The state diagram in figure 7 illustrates the individual steps of the automation.

Choose Test - The automation follows an iterative pattern and for each test, the first step is always the randomized selection

of a test, that had not been conducted yet.

Positioning - Depending on the type of test and the current position of the test subject, a starting position for the test is determined. Rotation gain tests will always be performed in the middle of the physical WFS area, while curvature gain tests will start in the closest corner. See figure 6 for all possible starting positions. The go-to target is then placed on the starting position for the test and its sound is activated. The sound will then keep running in a loop, until the test subject has reached a certain minimum proximity to the position. Upon arrival, the sound is turned of immediately and positioning is done.

Aligning - The starting alignment is also dependent on the type of test. Rotation gain tests always start with an alignment along the x-axis and curvature gain tests with an alignment, that allows the test subject to follow the manipulation towards the center of the room. See figure 6 for all possible starting alignments in regards to the starting position. The turn-to target is placed on a position in the proper direction and its sound is activated. The sound will then keep playing a loop, until a head orientation of the test subject had been captured, which is within a certain deviation to the calculated orientation towards the turn-to target. Then the sound will stop playing immediately and after a pause of two seconds, the aligning is done. This pause is to ensure, that the test subject has settled into that direction and to help distinguish between the sounds of the alignment and the following test.

Starting Tests - Before the manipulation can start, the corresponding virtual sound source has to be placed and activated. For curvature gain tests, the go-to target is placed at the position of the corner towards the test subject had just been oriented during the previous step. For rotation gain tests, the turn-to target is positioned outside of the physical WFS area in the opposite direction from the previous alignment. The next step is highly dependent on the type of test.

Curvature gain - For a curvature gain test, each decrease in distance towards the go-to target is multiplied by the value of the curvature gain to calculate the corresponding rotation of all virtual sound sources around the test subject. This state will be active, until the test subject has reached a distance to the starting position, which is higher, than the distance from the starting position to the go-to target. In this case, the test subject passed the go-to target, is most likely very close to the target and would now turn around to locate the exact position. Since this is not so much subject of the experiment and to speed up the process, the conditions are considered met.

Rotation gain - When a rotation gain test had been selected, all head rotations of the test subject will be multiplied with the value of the rotation gain and result in a corresponding rotation of all virtual sound sources around the test subject. This state will be active, until the difference between the orientation of the test subjects head and the angle towards the turn-to target is below a certain threshold. Then the manipulation will stop, but the sound will keep playing for another second, so the target does not just vanish during the rotation of the test subject.

Wrapup Test - The last step for each iteration is the wrap up. During the wrap up, the turn-to target and go-to target are muted, the test will be marked as done and removed from the to-do list and the to-do list is checked for more elements. If more tests need to be done, the iteration starts from the

Figure 7. State diagram of the automated test sequence.

beginning and otherwise, the experiment will end.

5.3 Gain values

The choice of the values of the gains to be tested is based on related work by Steinicke et al. [6] and modified by a couple of self conducted tests, to get good limits and distribution in between. Ideally, the greatest manipulations should be noticed by all test subjects and the smallest by none, to cover the whole range.

For rotation gains the range is $-60\% \leq g_R \leq +60\%$ with an increment of 5%. For curvature gains the range is $-1.0 \leq g_C \leq +1.0$, with $g_C := \frac{1}{r}$ and r being the radius of the circle that is defined by the curve, also with an increment of 0.05. Tests with a value of 0 are included four times each.

5.4 Test groups

The test subjects are to be divided into three major groups.

Group 1 are the *naive* test subjects. They do not know, that they are participating in a RDW experiment. Instead they are told, that the focus of the experiment is on the position preservation of focused sound sources. They will be asked to report whenever they feel, that a virtual sound source would move, even though it might just be a subjective perception.

Group 2 are the *aware* test subjects. They will be aware, that they are participating in a RDW experiment. They are instructed to report any notice of the virtual environment rotating around them. Presumably, this knowledge will influence the sensitivity of detecting the manipulations [10]. This is considered the most relevant group. Prospective users of an immersive virtual environment, which is using auditory RDW techniques, will most likely be aware, that these manipulations may occur.

Group 3 are the *expert* test subjects. They will know exactly, how the automation of the experiment is functioning. They will know the proportion of movements with manipulations to movements without manipulations and will most likely know in which situations a manipulation is likely to occur. All of them will have witnessed an experiment as a bystander and have an extensive discussion about the experiment beforehand. This group is considered the most challenging with presumably the highest detection rate.

The division into these groups will allow evaluation of the sensitivity to the manipulations regarding perceptibility in dependency to the knowledge of the system and situation.

6. IMPLEMENTATION

The system is implemented in Java 1.6 and based on the previously developed Motion Tracker-Wave Field Synthesis-

Figure 8. Processing sequence of the MoWeC.

Connector (MoWeC) [14]. This section will give a brief overview over the processing of the MoWeC, explaining the connection between the tracking system and the WFS system and how the RDW component had been integrated within.

6.1 Motion Tracker-Wave Field Synthesis-Connector (MoWeC)

The MoWeC is described in detail and in German language in [14]. Its processing sequence is illustrated in figure 8.

The MoWeC is driven by incoming network packages carrying tracking data, which is forwarded by the TrackerListener Application. This application provides a loose coupling between the MoWeC and its tracking system, while supplying the tracking data. The tracking data is then parsed and converted into the internal data type MoWeC source. The MoWeC is designed to work with these MoWeC sources.

The center of the MoWeC is defined by the optional components section. This is where the application logics can be implemented. Each optional component provides an application logic or a part of the overall application logic. Multiple

optional components can run at the same time, as long as they do not object each other logically. Optional components are modifying the MoWeC sources in respect of their position and orientation parameters etc..

After the optional component section, the MoWeC sources are converted into the target coordinate system of the WFS system. The changes are then transmitted to the WFS system and DAWs via open sound control (OSC) messages.

Simultaneously, the OSC listener receives all changes to the WFS system, which is converted into the internal coordinate system of the MoWeC and provided to the optional components.

6.2 Redirected walking component

As mentioned before, the RDW component is designed as an optional component for the MoWeC, as is illustrated in figure 8. As such, it is provided with tracking data from the tracking system and WFS data from the WFS system, both in form of MoWeC sources.

The tracking data from the head mounted target of the test subject provides the RDW component with position and orientation data for the head of the test subject. According to the currently defined gain, a rotation value is calculated as described in section 5.2.3. This rotation value will be used to calculate new coordinates and orientations for all other MoWeC sources, to give the impression, that the whole scene is rotating around the test subject. The MoWeC delivers these changes to the WFS system and the DAW in form of OSC messages.

The RDW component has its own graphical user interface (GUI). Starting this, the MoWeC's GUI is bypassed and a number of settings are predefined, which otherwise would have to be set manually. Processing can be started and stopped and different gains can be set manually. Further the activated gain is shown, logging and tracking can be (de-)activated, as well as the automated test started. The automated tests can be named for logging purposes. For the experiment at hand, manual (de-)activation of gains is not necessary however. By starting the automated test, gains will be chosen and applied automatically.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Methods have been developed, to identify thresholds for the detection of RDW manipulations via auditory cues by a WFS system. Even though general RDW had increasing attention, the auditory aspect was mostly neglected. This paper describes the preparation for an experiment to identify detection thresholds for a selection of RDW methods.

Following this paper, the experiment will be conducted with approximately 30 test subjects to identify thresholds depending of various factors like knowledge of the system, time in the system, walking and turning speed.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] S. Razzaque, Z. Kohn, and M. C. Whitton, "Redirected Walking," Chapel Hill, NC, USA, Tech. Rep., 2001.
- [2] J. Dichgans and T. Brandt, "Visual-Vestibular Interaction: Effects on Self-Motion Perception and Postural Control," in *Perception*, ser. Handbook of Sensory Physiology, R. Held, H. Leibowitz, and H.-L. Teuber, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1978, vol. 8, pp. 755–804.
- [3] J. Lackner, "Induction of illusory self-rotation and nystagmus by a rotating sound-field," *Aviation, space, and environmental medicine*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 129–131, February 1977.
- [4] C. Neth, J. Souman, D. Engel, U. Kloos, H. Bülthoff, and B. Mohler, "Velocity-Dependent Dynamic Curvature Gain for Redirected Walking," *Visualization and Computer Graphics, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 18, no. 7, pp. 1041–1052, July 2012.
- [5] F. Steinicke, G. Bruder, L. Kohli, J. Jerald, and K. Hinrichs, "Taxonomy and Implementation of Redirection Techniques for Ubiquitous Passive Haptic Feedback," in *Cyberworlds, 2008 International Conference on*, Sept 2008, pp. 217–223.
- [6] F. Steinicke, G. Bruder, K. Hinrichs, J. Jerald, H. Frenz, and M. Lappe, "Real walking through virtual environments by redirection techniques," *JVRB*, vol. 6(2009), no. 2, 2009.
- [7] F. Steinicke, T. Ropinski, G. Bruder, K. Hinrichs, H. Frenz, and M. Lappe, "A Universal Virtual Locomotion System: Supporting Generic Redirected Walking and Dynamic Passive Haptics within Legacy 3D Graphics Applications," in *Virtual Reality Conference, 2008. VR '08. IEEE*, March 2008, pp. 291–292.
- [8] S. Serafin, N. Nilsson, E. Siktstrom, A. De Goetzen, and R. Nordahl, "Estimation of Detection Thresholds for Acoustic Based Redirected Walking Techniques," in *Virtual Reality (VR), 2013 IEEE*, March 2013, pp. 161–162.
- [9] F. Steinicke, G. Bruder, J. Jerald, H. Frenz, and M. Lappe, "Analyses of Human Sensitivity to Redirected Walking," in *Proceedings of the 2008 ACM Symposium on VRST*, ser. VRST '08. New York, NY, USA: ACM, October 2008, pp. 149–156.
- [10] —, "Estimation of Detection Thresholds for Redirected Walking Techniques," *Visualization and Computer Graphics, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 17–27, Jan 2010.
- [11] E. B. Goldstein, *Sensation and Perception*. Boston, MA: Cengage Learning, 2010.
- [12] F. Steinicke, G. Bruder, T. Ropinski, K. H. Hinrichs, H. Frenz, and M. Lappe, "Generic Redirected Walking & Dynamic Passive Haptics: Evaluation and Implications for Virtual Locomotion Interfaces," in *Proceedings of IEEE Symposium on 3DUI (Poster Presentation)*. IEEE Press, 2008, pp. 147–148.
- [13] W. Fohl, "The wave field synthesis lab at the haw hamburg," in *Sound-Perception-Performance*. Springer, 2013, pp. 243–255.
- [14] M. Nogalski, "Gestengesteuerte Positionierung von Klangquellen einer Wellenfeldsynthese-Anlage mit Hilfe eines kamerabasierten 3D-Tracking-Systems," Bachelor Thesis, Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, 2012.